

Characterization and Mitigation of Droplet-Induced Impact Damage in Wind Blade Leading-edge Coatings

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Outline

1. Introduction & Background
2. Calibration & Setup Optimization
3. Material Evaluation for Stress Wave Dissipation
4. Summary and Future Work

Leading Edge Erosion Damage

Percentage of reported part failures

25% of the levelized cost

Blade lifetime decline (7%↑)

Annual energy production reduce (5%↑)

Other blade damage

Elhadi Ibrahim, et al., Materials, 2020
Mishnaevsky, et al., Wind Energy, 2020

Shohag, et al., Wind Engineering, 2017
Mishnaevsky, Renewable Energy, 2019

Leading-Edge Erosion Mechanism

- Erosion is caused by the high-velocity impact of rain droplets near the blade tip
- The impact induces stress waves that lead to fatigue damage of the surface coating

Simulate Droplet Impact Using Laser-induced Stress Waves

Laser Induced Stress Waves Setup

Change of fringes over time $n(t)$

Displacement over time $u(t)$

Substrate stress over time $\sigma_{\text{sub}}(t)$

Interferometric Data Analysis

Output Voltage Signal $V(t)$

$$V(t) = \frac{V_{max} + V_{min}}{2} + \frac{V_{max} - V_{min}}{2} \sin(2\pi n(t))$$

Displacement $u(t)$

$$u(t) = \frac{\lambda_0 n(t)}{2}$$

Substrate Stress $\sigma_{sub}(t)$

$$\sigma_{sub}(t) = -\frac{1}{2} (\rho C_d)_{sub} \frac{du}{dt}$$

Energy / Area $J(t)$

$$J(t) = \int_0^t \sigma_{sub} \frac{du}{dt} dt$$

Calibration & Setup Optimization

Effect of Confining Layer Thickness

Investigate the impact of the confining layer thickness on controlling the generation and measurement of stress waves.

Material Evaluation for Stress Wave Dissipation

Polyurethane Coating Preparation

PU Coating Preparation :

Etch the glass substrate using 30% nitric acid → Apply a 40 μm Kapton spacer → Mix and degas the PU components → Drop-cast the PU resin onto the etched substrate → Place a second glass substrate on top to form the sandwich structure → Vitrify at room temperature for 24 hours → Cure in an oven at 50 °C for 24 hours

Components	Desmodur E 30700	1,4 butanediol	DABCO	MgSO ₄
Mole ratio	1	1	0.05	0.05
Role	Isocyanate prepolymer	Chain extender	Catalyst	Desiccant

Polystyrene Coating Preparation

PS Coating Preparation :

Etch the glass substrate using 30% nitric acid → Prepare a 5 wt% solution of polystyrene in toluene
→ Sonicate the solution for 1 hour → Spin coat the solution at 5000 rpm (ramp: 15 s, dwell: 30 s) →
Dry the coated sample in a toluene-saturated environment

Spin coating steps	Ramp	Dwell	RPM
Time (s)	15	30	5000

Polyurethane Coating Stress Wave Dissipation

PU sample stacking	Sandwich
Water glass	8 μ m
PU coating	40 μ m
Reflection	200 nm

Polystyrene Coating Stress Wave Dissipation

PS sample stacking	Sandwich
Water glass	4 μm
PS coating	0.5 μm
Reflection	200 nm

Preliminary Comparison of Stress Wave Energy Absorption by PU and PS Coatings

We evaluated the stress wave energy absorption by polyurethane (PU) and polystyrene (PS) coatings compared to an uncoated control

Total transmitted energy $J(t)$ (J/m^2)

$$J(t) = \int_0^t \sigma_{sub} \frac{du}{dt} dt$$

Percent energy absorption (%)

$$= \frac{J_0 - J(t)}{J_0}$$

J_0 : Transmitted energy of the substrate stress

$J(t)$: Transmitted energy of the sample without coating

The effects of thickness on dissipation will be studied in future work.

Summary

- Developed a high-throughput, material-efficient laser-induced stress wave platform for evaluating erosion-mitigating coatings on coupon-scale samples.
- Demonstrated tunable stress wave generation by adjusting laser fluence and confinement layer thickness.
- Preliminary results show both polyurethane (PU) and polystyrene (PS) coatings reduce transmitted stress wave energy compared to uncoated samples.
- Future work will incorporate self-healing functionality and dynamic networks into coatings to achieve active mitigation of erosion damage.

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